

Trend and Causes of Maternal Mortality at a Tertiary University Teaching Hospital in Sub-Saharan Africa: A 10-Year Review

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Maternal death is the death of a woman while she is pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy, for any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management, but not from accidental or incidental causes. This study is aimed at analyzing the causes of maternal mortality in a tertiary health institution in Southern Nigeria.

Methodology: This was a retrospective study among 398 participants selected using incidental non-probability sampling technique from the healthcare records of mothers on admission in the maternity ward of University of Uyo Teaching Hospital during the period January 2006 - November 2016.

Results: 30.3 per cent of maternal deaths in the period under consideration were due to obstetric haemorrhage, 20.4 per cent from obstetric sepsis, and 13.5 per cent from hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, 10.2 per cent from complications of abortion and 9.3 per cent from severe anaemia. The age group 25-34 had the highest incidence of maternal mortality in this study (45.2%). Participants who had secondary level of education had the highest number of maternal deaths (64.3%). Participants who resided in rural areas also had the most incidences of maternal deaths (61.8%).

Conclusion: Direct causes were predominantly responsible for maternal deaths in this study.

Keywords: maternal mortality

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INTRODUCTION

Maternal death, as defined by the Bureau of Vital Statistics, is the death of a woman while she is pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy, for any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management, but not from accidental or incidental causes^{1,2}. The American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology (ACOG), Centre for Disease Control (CDC), and Pregnancy Mortality Surveillance System (PMSS) define maternal mortality as the death of any woman occurring during pregnancy or within 1 year after the end of pregnancy resulting from complications of the pregnancy, a chain of events initiated by the pregnancy, or the aggravation of an unrelated condition by the physiologic effects of the pregnancy or its management^{3,4}.

Further classification of a pregnancy-related death identifies the cause of death as direct, indirect, unrelated, or

undetermined as related to pregnancy⁵. Direct maternal death is the death of a woman resulting from obstetric complications of pregnancy, labor and puerperium; from interventions, omissions or incorrect treatment; or from a chain of events resulting from any of the above while indirect maternal death is the death of a woman resulting from a previously existing disease or a disease that developed during pregnancy and was not due to direct obstetric causes but was aggravated by the physiological effects of pregnancy⁶. An unrelated death results from causes not related to the pregnancy or its complications or treatment, and undetermined deaths are those in which a definite cause of death is not established⁵.

Maternal mortality remains a global public health problem. Nigeria has one of the highest maternal mortality in the world. Published estimates show that 287,000 maternal deaths occur annually with majority of them occurring in

developing countries⁷. In 2008, more than 50% of all maternal deaths were in only six countries namely India, Nigeria, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Ethiopia and Democratic Republic of the Congo⁸. The average maternal mortality rate in Nigeria is estimated to be 704/100,000 live births, although this ranges from 165 to 1549 deaths per 100,000 live births in the South-Western and North-Eastern parts of the country, respectively⁸.

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals aim at reducing the global maternal mortality ratio to less than 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030⁹. This study is aimed at analyzing the causes of maternal mortality in a tertiary health institution in Southern Nigeria.

II. METHODOLOGY

Study Location

University of Uyo Teaching Hospital is a tertiary healthcare institution located in the state capital, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State is a state in Nigeria located on the southern part of the country lying between latitudes 4°32'N and 5°33'N, and longitudes 7°25'E and 8°25'E with a population of over 5 million people.

Study Design

This was a retrospective study using past clinical records in University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Ethical approval was received from the Ethical Review Board of Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Health.

Sample

398 participants were selected after calculating for sample size¹⁰⁻¹⁴ using incidental non-probability sampling technique from the healthcare records of mothers on admission in the maternity ward of University of Uyo Teaching Hospital during the period January 2006 - November 2016. The sample comprised of mothers who died while on admission and qualified as maternal deaths.

Measure

The dependent variable was maternal death. Direct obstetric death variables included obstetrical hemorrhage (antepartum hemorrhage and postpartum hemorrhage), postpartum sepsis, spontaneous or induced abortion, hypertensive diseases, obstructed labor, ruptured uterus, embolism and anesthetic complications. Indirect obstetric death variables included, but not limited to, anemia, HIV, cardiac diseases, diabetes, renal disease, and malaria.

Analysis

The questionnaires were carefully examined for correctness and completeness, coded and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 for Windows. Quantitative data generated from the study was presented in

form of tables and analysed as descriptive frequencies and percentages.

III. RESULTS

Table I shows the proportion of causes of maternal deaths among cases defined in this study. 30.3 per cent of maternal deaths in the period under consideration were due to obstetric haemorrhage, 20.4 per cent from obstetric sepsis, and 13.5 per cent from hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, 10.2 per cent from complications of abortion and 9.3 per cent from severe anaemia.

Table II shows the distribution of different socio-demographic variables. The age group 25-34 had the highest incidence of maternal mortality in this study (45.2%). Participants who had secondary level of education had the highest number of maternal deaths (64.3%). Participants who resided in rural areas also had the most incidences of maternal deaths (61.8%).

Figure I is a bar chart showing distribution of maternal deaths among direct and indirect causes.

Table I: Causes of Maternal Deaths

Causes	Number (%)
<u>Direct</u>	
Obstetric haemorrhage	30.3
Obstetric sepsis	20.4
Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy	13.5
Abortions complications	10.2
HIV	9.0
Complications of Diabetes in Pregnancy	3.2
<u>Indirect</u>	
Severe anaemia	9.3
Others	4.1

Figure I: Causes of Maternal Deaths

Causes of Maternal Deaths in University of Uyo Teaching Hospital

meta-chart.com

Table II: Socio-demographic Distribution of Maternal Deaths

Socio-demographic Variable	n (%)
Age	
15–24	136(34.2)
25–34	180(45.2)
>34	82(20.6)
Total	398(100)
Education level	
Primary	102(25.6)
Secondary	256(64.3)
Tertiary	40(10.1)
Total	398(100)
Residence type	
a) Urban	152(38.2)
b) Rural	246(61.8)
Total	398(100)
Marital status	
a) Married	362(91.0)
b) Not married	36(9.0)
Total	398(100)

IV. DISCUSSION

In this study, direct causes of accounted for 86.6 per cent of maternal mortality and they included obstetric haemorrhage (30.3%), obstetric sepsis (20.4%), hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (13.5%), abortions complications (10.2%), HIV(9.0%) and complications of diabetes in pregnancy(3.2%). Indirect causes accounted for 13.4% of maternal deaths and the most common indirect cause was anaemia in pregnancy (9.3%).

A study in Port Harcourt reported direct causes to account for 80% of maternal deaths while indirect cause accounted for 20% with cardiovascular disorders in the majority. The most common indirect cause of death was anemia (7.01%) making it the fifth leading cause of death in their study¹⁵. The trend of maternal mortality in this study is also similar to this study with anaemia also being the fifth commonest cause of maternal mortality. It is also worth to mention that Port Harcourt and Uyo (where this study was done) are located in the same geographical region in Southern Nigeria and share a border.

In Lagos, Daramola *et al.* found out that about 81% of autopsy certified maternal deaths were due to direct causes. The same study showed the three leading causes of maternal deaths were obstetric hemorrhage (25.61%), genital sepsis (19.68%), and pregnancy-induced hypertension (16.71%)¹⁶. This is similar to our finding in this study.

Another study reported that 71.4% of maternal deaths were due to the direct cause, consisting of obstetric hemorrhage, complications of unsafe induced abortion and complications of labor¹⁷. This percentage is lower than our study, but the two leading causes of death are inclusive in both studies. The indirect causes reported in the same study included non-genital infections, anemia in pregnancy and preexisting hypertension. Pre-existing hypertension is classified under hypertension in pregnancy; hence delineating it singly is somewhat unfeasible.

A study in South Africa identified unsafe abortion as a major cause of maternal mortality¹⁸. Another study showed that direct causes accounted for 38.2% of maternal deaths with hemorrhage as the most frequent cause (16.6%). Other causes included puerperal sepsis and eclampsia (8.7% each), post-caesarean section septicemia and ectopic pregnancy both accounted for 1.4%. Indirect causes conditions accounted for 56.1% to include HIV/AIDS, pyogenic bronchopneumonia, severe malaria, and pyogenic meningitis¹⁹. Another study in India reported that pregnancy induced hypertension, anemia, septicemia, and haemorrhage from the genital tract were the leading causes of death respectively²⁰.

A previous study analysed the causes of maternal death in Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean. Haemorrhage was seen to be the leading cause of death in Africa and in Asia. Hypertensive disorders caused majority of the maternal deaths in Latin America and the Caribbean. The study concluded that haemorrhage and hypertensive

disorders are leading causes of maternal deaths in developing countries²¹.

Another study examined the causes of maternal deaths and stillbirths at Wad Medani, Sudan between 2003 and 2007. All maternal deaths and stillbirths during this period were reviewed and classified retrospectively. Septicaemia was the most common cause of the maternal deaths followed by obstructed labour or abortion-related sepsis, viral hepatitis, haemorrhage, preeclampsia/eclampsia, and malaria²².

A previous study also assessed the aetiology, trends and causes of maternal mortality (MM) in Tanta University Hospital. They consulted files for each case of maternal mortality from the period between 2007 and 2009. Their analysis revealed that the main cause of maternal deaths were postpartum haemorrhage, caesarean section, preeclampsia/eclampsia, sepsis and embolic phenomena²³. Another study in South Africa was conducted with the objective of determining the clinical and demographic profile of maternal deaths and also to determine the most common primary causes of maternal deaths at district hospital level. The findings from the study indicated that the five leading causes of deaths were non-pregnancy-related sepsis, miscarriage, acute collapse, pregnancy-related sepsis and anaesthetic complications²⁴.

V. CONCLUSION

Nigeria is away from achieving the SDG Goal for reduction of maternal mortality by a significant proportion. The major causes of maternal deaths were haemorrhage, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and sepsis. Socio-demographic variables that were associated with a higher incidence of maternal mortality were living in a rural area and secondary level of education.

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